

Supplementary Table S2. *Boeckella* species list included in the present study. Literature references of samples published before are given below. Sequences obtained from Barcode of Life System (BOLD System) and Genebank repositories, augmented by fresh collections during expeditions of authors (CSM, SR, JN, CGW, EP, PC and JJ). Location details[‡] of each sampled specimen were detailed in the occurrence dataset published in Global Biodiversity and Information Facility (GBIF).

Species	Biogeographic Region	Collection locality	Reference	Associated Repository	<i>cox1</i>	28S rRNA	ITS1/ITS2	Phylogenetic Analyses	Morphological Revision
<i>B. antiqua</i>	South America	Río Negro. Argentina	1	GenBank	DQ356541.1	GU049733.1		*	
<i>B. bergi</i>	South America	Santa Cruz. Argentina	1, 2	GenBank	DQ356543.1	GU049734.1		*	
<i>B. brasiliensis</i>	South America	Brunswick Peninsula Chile		GBIF	Present study			*	*
<i>B. brevicaudata</i>	South America	Navarino Island		GBIF	Present study			*	*
<i>B. brevicaudata</i>	sub-Antarctic Islands	Kerguelen Island		GBIF	Present study			*	*
<i>B. diamantina</i>	South America	Mendoza. Argentina	1	GenBank	DQ356548.1 DQ356549.1 DQ356550.1			*	
<i>B. gibbosa</i>	South America	Mendoza. Argentina	1	GenBank	DQ356551.1 DQ356552.1 DQ356553.1			*	
<i>B. gracilis</i>	South America	Buenos Aires. Argentina	1	GenBank	DQ356555.1			*	
<i>B. meteoris</i>	South America	Santa Cruz. Argentina	1, 2	GenBank	DQ356561.1 DQ356558.1 DQ356557.1 DQ356560.1	GU049738.1		*	*
<i>B. meteoris</i>	South America	Porvenir. Tierra del Fuego		BOLD GBIF	Present study			*	*
<i>B. meteoris</i>	South America	Torres del Paine National Park		BOLD GBIF	Present study			*	*
<i>B. michaelseni</i>	South America	Tierra del Fuego. Argentina	1,2	GenBank	DQ356564.1 DQ356563.1 DQ356562.1	GU049742.1		*	*

<i>B. michaelsoni</i>	South America	Falkland/Malvinas Islands	3	BOLD GBIF					*
<i>B. michaelsoni</i>	Sub-Antarctic Islands	South Georgia	3	BOLD GBIF					
<i>B. poopoensis</i>	South America	Buenos Aires. Argentina	1	GenBank	DQ356565.1			*	
<i>B. poopoensis</i>	South America	Chubut. Argentina	1, 2	GenBank	DQ356566.1	GU049746.1		*	
<i>B. poppei</i>	South America	Tierra del Fuego. Argentina	1, 2	GenBank	DQ356568.1	GU049749.1		*	
<i>B. poppei</i>	South America	Peninsula Brunswick		GBIF	Present study			*	*
<i>B. poppei</i>	Sub-Antarctic Islands	South Georgia		GBIF	Present study			*	*
<i>B. poppei</i>	Maritime Antarctica	South Shetland Islands		GBIF	Present study			*	*
<i>B. poppei</i>	Maritime Antarctica	Signy Island		GBIF	Present study			*	*
<i>B. poppei</i>	Maritime Antarctica	Antarctic Peninsula		GBIF	Present study			*	*
<i>B. poppei</i>	Continental Antarctica	Terrasovoje Lake, Amery Oasis	4	GenBank		AY997791 AY997795 AY997794		*	
<i>B. titicacae</i>	South America	Lake Titicaca. Bolivia	5	GenBank	GQ426055.1 GQ426056.1			*	
<i>B. titicacae</i>	South America	Surire Salt lake. Northern Chile	5	GenBank	GQ426054.1			*	
<i>B. titicacae</i>	South America	Northern Chile	5	GenBank	GQ426056.1			*	
<i>B. vallentini</i>	Sub-Antarctic Islands	Kerguelen Islands		BOLD GBIF	Present study			*	*
<i>B. vallentini</i>	Sub-Antarctic Islands	Possession Island. Crozet		BOLD GBIF	Present study			*	*
<i>B. delicata</i>	Australasia	New Zealand		BOLD, GBIF	NZPL001-09 NZPL002-09			*	
<i>B. delicata</i>	Australasia	Waikato. New Zealand		BOLD, GBIF	NZPL003-09				

Supplementary Material

<i>B. fluvialis</i>	Australasia	New South Wales. Australia		BOLD, GBIF	NZPL008-09 NZPL004-09 NZPL007-09	NZPL004_09 NZPL007_09 NZPL006_09 NZPL008-09		*	
<i>B. fluvialis</i>	Australasia	New South Wales. Australia	5	GenBank		GU0495753.1		*	
<i>B. hamata</i>	Australasia	New Zealand		BOLD, GBIF	NZPL009-09 NZPL010-09 NZPL011-09	NZPL009-09 NZPL011-09 NZPL012-09		*	
<i>B. major</i>	Australasia	Australia, Tasmania		BOLD GBIF					*
<i>B. minuta</i>	Australasia	New Zealand, Australia		BOLD GBIF					*
<i>B. montana</i>	Australasia	New South Wales. Australia		BOLD GBIF				*	*
<i>B. nyoraensis</i>	Australasia	Australia, Tasmania		BOLD GBIF					*
<i>B. propinqua</i>	Australasia	New Zealand		BOLD, GBIF	NZPL026-09 NZPL027-09 NZPL028-09 NZPL029-09 NZPL030-09	NZPL026_09 NZPL444-10		*	*
<i>B. pseudochelae</i>	Australasia	New South Wales. Australia		BOLD, GBIF	NZPL033-09 NZPL034-09	NZPL032		*	*
<i>B. symmetrica</i>	Australasia	New Zealand		BOLD, GBIF	NZPL035-09 NZPL036-09 NZPL183-10	NZPL472-10 NZPL471-10 NZPL440-10 NZPL460-10 NZPL465-10 NZPL466-10		*	
<i>B. symmetrica</i>	Australasia	Australia		BOLD, GBIF	NZPL037-09 NZPL182-10			*	
<i>B. tanea</i>	Australasia	New Zealand		BOLD, GBIF	NZPL568-12 NZPLR167-11	NZPL567		*	
<i>B. triarticulata</i>	Australasia	Australia		BOLD, GBIF	NZPL038-09 NZPL039-09 NZPLR139-11 NZPLR138-11				

<i>B. triarticulata</i>	Australasia	South West Australia	3	BOLD, GBIF		GU049756.1 GU049755.1			
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‡ = Longitudes and latitudes found via <https://www.gbif.org/es/dataset/474ee54a-9eae-4b67-b79b-d8fc2d9ec884>

* = Sequences included in the phylogenetic/morphological analyses conducted in this study.

Samples or GenBank sequences used from references: 1: Adamowicz et al. 2007; 2: Adamowicz et al. 2010; 3: Menu-Marque et al. 2000; 4: Bisset et al. 2005; 5: Scheihing et al. 2010

References:

1. Adamowicz, S.J., Menu-Marque, S., Hebert, P.D. & Purvis, A. (2007) Molecular systematics and patterns of morphological evolution in the Centropagidae (Copepoda: Calanoida) of Argentina. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society*, **90**, 279–292
 2. Adamowicz, S.J., Menu-Marque, S., Halse, S.A., Topan, J.C., Zemlak, T.S., Hebert, P.D.N. & Witt, J.D.S. (2010) The evolutionary diversification of the Centropagidae (Crustacea, Calanoida): a history of habitat shifts. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution*, **55**, 418–30.
 3. Menu-Marque, S., Morrone, J.J. & Locascio, C. (2000) Distributional pattern of the South American species of *Boeckella* (Copepoda: Centropagidae): A track analysis. *Journal of Crustacean Biology*, **20**, 262–272.
- Bissett, A., Gibson, J.A.E., Jarman, S.N., Swadling, K.M. & Cromer, L. (2005) Isolation, amplification, and identification of ancient copepod DNA from lake sediments. *Limnology and Oceanography-Methods*, **3**, 533–542
4. Scheihing, R., Cardenas, L., Nespolo, R.F., Krall, P., Walz, K., Kohshima, S. & Labarca, P. (2009) Morphological and molecular analysis of centropagids from the high Andean plateau (Copepoda: Calanoidea). *Hydrobiologia*, **637**, 45–52

Supplementary Fig. S1. Bayesian maximum clade credibility tree of *Boeckella* relationships based on nucDNA (28S rRNA, ITS1/ITS2) and mtDNA (cox1) sequences. Bayesian posterior probability support values are shown above the nodes. The polyphyletic *B. poppei* clades are indicated by (i), (ii) and (iii). AM: Maritime Antarctic; SG: South Georgia; SA: South America; FLK: Falkland/Malvinas Is.; CRZ: Crozet; KER: Kerguelen; Mg: Magallanes; TF: Tierra del Fuego; IH: Hornos Island.

Supplementary Fig. S2. Bayesian maximum clade credibility tree of *Boeckella* relationships based on 28S rRNA. Bayesian posterior probability support values are shown above the nodes. The polyphyletic *B. poppei* clades are indicated by (i), (ii) and (iii).

Supplementary Table S3. Sequences list included in *cox1* phylogenetic analysis displayed in Supplementary Fig S4. Sequences retrieved from Genbank and BOLD System are identified with a prefix code.

Label	Sequences
Hap_1	DQ356562.1_Bmichaelseni DQ356563.1_Bmichaelseni DQ356564.1_Bmichaelseni
Hap_2	DQ356548.1_Bdiamantina DQ356549.1_Bdiamantina DQ356550.1_Bdiamantina
Hap_3	DQ356565.1_Bpoopoensis DQ356566.1_Bpoopoensis
Hap_4	DQ356567.1_Bpoopoensis
Hap_5	IH02_Hornos_Is
Hap_6	IH04_Hornos_Is IH05_Boeck_Is IH07_Boeck_Is IH08_Boeck_Is
Hap_7	IH01_Hornos_Is
Hap_8	DQ356571.1_Psarsi
Hap_9	DQ356559.1_Bmeteoris
Hap_10	DQ356561.1_Bmeteoris
Hap_11	CSTP34_Bmeteoris
Hap_12	LSC02_Bmeteoris
Hap_13	POV42_Bmeteoris
Hap_14	DQ356557.1_Bmeteoris DQ356560.1_Bmeteoris
Hap_15	NZPL020_09B_minuta NZPL022_09B_minuta NZPL023_09B_minuta NZPL024_09B_minuta
Hap_16	NZPL021_09B_minuta
Hap_17	KRG01_Bbrevicaudata KRG02_Bbrevicaudata KRG04_Bbrevicaudata

Hap_18	PLR09_Bbravicaudata DQ356547.1_Bbrevicaudata PLR10_Bbravicaudata
Hap_19	Ptr08_Bbravicaudata
Hap_20	NZPL032_09B_pseudocheilae
Hap_21	NZPL033_09B_pseudocheilae NZPL034_09B_pseudocheilae
Hap_22	DQ356543.1_Bbergi
Hap_23	DQ356555.1_Bgracilis
Hap_24	DQ356556.1_Bgracilis
Hap_25	DQ356551.1_Bgibbosa DQ356552.1_Bgibbosa DQ356553.1_Bgibbosa
Hap_26	CRZ01_Bvallentini CRZ02_Bvallentini CRZ03_Bvallentini
Hap_27	KRG05_Bvallentini KRG07_Bvallentini KRG08_Bvallentini
Hap_28	DQ356541.1_Bantiqua
Hap_29	DQ356542.1_Bantiqua
Hap_30	DQ356544.1_Bbrasiliensis
Hap_31	UP02_Bbravicaudata
Hap_32	UP04_Bbravicaudata
Hap_33	DQ356545.1_Bbrasiliensis Bag01_Bbrasiliensis LRD03_Bbrasiliensis
Hap_34	PQN03_Bbrasiliensis PQN05_Bbrasiliensis
Hap_35	SGR02_Bbrasiliensis
Hap_36	RV14_Bbrasiliensis
Hap_37	Bpoppei_AM
Hap_38	Bpoppei_AM
Hap_39	Bpoppei_AM

Hap_40	Bpoppei_AM
Hap_41	Bpoppei_Pat
Hap_42	Bpoppei_AM
Hap_43	Bpoppei_AM
Hap_44	Bpoppei_subAntarctic
Hap_45	Bpoppei_subAntarctic
Hap_46	Bpoppei_subAntarctic
Hap_47	Bpoppei_Pat
Hap_48	Bpoppei_Pat
Hap_49	FLK1_01 FLK1_02 FLK1_03 FLK1_04
Hap_50	FLK1_05
Hap_51	DQ356568.1_Bpoppei
Hap_52	DQ356576.1_Bpoppei
Hap_53	SGR03 SGR04
Hap_54	DQ356569.1_Bpoppei DQ356570.1_Bpoppei
Hap_55	DQ356554.1_Bgracilipes
Hap_56	NZPL035_09B_symmetrica NZPL036_09B_symmetrica NZPL037_09B_symmetrica NZPL182_10B_symmetrica NZPL183_10B_symmetrica
Hap_57	NZPLR139_11B_triarticulata
Hap_58	NZPLR138_11B_triarticulata
Hap_59	NZPL038_09B_triarticulata NZPL039_09B_triarticulata
Hap_60	NZPL448_10B_triarticulata
Hap_61	NZPL008_09B_fluvialis

Hap_62	NZPL004_09B_fluvialis NZPL005_09B_fluvialis NZPL006_09B_fluvialis
Hap_63	NZPL007_09B_fluvialis
Hap_64	NZPL009_09B_hamata NZPL010_09B_hamata NZPL011_09B_hamata
Hap_65	NZPL012_09B_hamata NZPL013_09B_hamata
Hap_66	NZPL026_09B_propinqua NZPL027_09B_propinqua NZPL029_09B_propinqua NZPL030_09B_propinqua NZPL028_09B_propinqua
Hap_67	NZPL025_09B_montana
Hap_68	NZPL001_09B_delicata NZPL002_09B_delicata NZPL003_09B_delicata
Hap_69	NZPL567_12B_tanea
Hap_70	NZPL568_12B_tanea NZPLR167_11B_tanea

Supplementary Fig. S5: Haplotype network of 28S rRNA of *Boeckella poppei* populations including ancient and modern DNA from the Prince Charles Mountains in continental Antarctica. These rRNA sequences were associated with *Boeckella poppei* clade (i) from Fig.2a, and Supplementary Figure S2.

Appendix S1. Kit *QIAGEN DNA Easy Tissue* modify protocol

1. Use the whole individual and dry all the residual ethanol
2. Add **90 μ L Buffer ATL**
3. Add **20 μ L Proteinase K**. Mix thoroughly by vortexing, and incubate at 56°C overnight (6-10 hrs) on a rocking platform until the tissue is completely lysed
4. Vortex for 15 s
5. Add **12 μ L Proteinase K** and incubate in a water bath at **60°C** for **1h**. Vortex occasionally during incubation to disperse the sample every 15m
6. Add **100 μ L Buffer AL** and **100 μ L ethanol** (96-100%) and mix thoroughly by vortexing immediately after to yield a homogeneous solution.
7. Pipette the mixture from step 6 (including any precipitate) into the DNeasy Mini spin column placed in a 2 mL collection tube (provided).
8. Centrifuge at 8000 RPM for 1min. Discard flow-through.
9. Add **250 μ L Buffer AW1** and centrifuge at **8000RPM** for **1min**. Discard flow-through
10. Place the DNeasy Mini spin column in a new 2 mL collection tube (provided), add **250 μ L Buffer AW2**
11. Centrifuge for **3min at 14000RPM** to dry the DNeasy membrane. Discard flow-through and collection tube
12. Place the DNeasy Mini spin column in a clean 1.5 mL tube and add **50 μ L Buffer AE** directly onto the DNeasy Mini membrane.
13. Incubate at room temperature for 1 min and then centrifuge for **1 min at 8000 RPM**
14. Repeat step 13 passing again the **50 μ L flow-through** the membrane. This step leads to increased overall DNA yield.

Appendix S2. Primers for *Boeckella*. The segment of the mitochondrial cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (*cox1*) was amplified using newly-designed *Boeckella* primers modified from universal primers LCO1490 and HCO2918 (Folmer *et al.*, 1994), and two segments of the 28S rRNA gene, using universal primers LSU5 and ECD2 (Littlewood *et al.*, 2000; Olson *et al.*, 2003) and the Internal Transcribed Spacers ITS1 kp2 and ITS2 28s (Presa *et al.*, 2002).

cytochrome c oxidase subunit I (*cox1*)

Modified from Folmer *et al.* 1994

43F_Boeck 5' CGAATAGAATTAGGTCAAGC 3'

485R_Boeck 5' GCAAATAAAGGTATTCGATCT 3'

28S rRNA

Littlewood *et al.* 2000 and Olson *et al.* 2003

LSU5 (F) 5' TAGGTCGACCCGCTGAAYTTAAGCA 3'

ECD2 (R): 5' CTTGGTCCGTGTTTCAAGACGG 3'

Internal Transcribed Spacers 1 and 2 (ITS1/ITS2)

Presa *et al.* 2002

ITS1 kp2 5' AAAAAGCTTCCGTAGGTGAACCTGCG 3'

ITS2 28s 5' ATATGCTTAAATTCAGCGGG 3'

Appendix S3. PCR Mix protocol. PCR amplifications were performed separately for each gene following each reference for thermal cycle protocol. For *cox1* we conducted several settings for PCR thermal cycle and mix reaction. Purification and sequencing was carried out in both directions by Macrogen Inc. (Seoul, South Korea).

For ***cox1*** 2.5 μL 10X Buffer (50 mM KCl, 10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.0), 0.9 μL of 50 mM MgCl₂, 200 mM dNTPs, 1 μL of each primer (10 pg/mL), 0.5 μL BSA 10 mg/mL, 1 U Taq polymerase (Invitrogen), 14.5 μL of double-distilled water and 4 μL of DNA. Thermal cycling parameters for *cox1* were modified from Scheihing et al., (2009), and included an initial denaturation step at 94°C for 1 min, followed by 10 cycles at 94°C for 1 min, 40°C for 90 sec and 72°C for 1 min, followed by 30 cycles at 94°C for 1 min, 46°C for 90 sec and 72°C for 90 sec, and a final 10 min extension at 72°C. For **28S** PCR reaction 2.5 μL 10X Buffer, 1 μL 50 mM MgCl₂, 200 mM dNTPs, 1 μL of each primer (10 pg/mL), 0.3 μL BSA 10 mg/mL, 1 U Taq polymerase (Invitrogen), 16.05 μL of double-distilled water and 2 μL of DNA. The PCR regime was as follows 94°C for 5 min, followed by 30 cycles at 94°C for 90 sec, 54°C for 90 sec and 72°C for 2 min and a final 5 min extension at 72°C. For **ITS1/ITS2** the PCR reaction used 2.5 μL 10X Buffer, 0.3 μL 50 mM MgCl₂, 200 mM dNTPs, 1 μL of each primer (10 pg/mL), 0.5 μL BSA 10 mg/mL, 1 U Taq polymerase (Promega), 16.9 μL of double-distilled water and 2 μL of DNA. The PCR regime was 95°C for 5 min, followed by 43 cycles of 95°C for 90 sec, 55°C for 2 min and 72°C for 3 min and a final 10 min extension at 72°C.